

COOPERATION OF SCHOOL, FAMILY AND NEIGHBORHOOD IN PROVIDING ENVIRONMENTAL AND LEGAL EDUCATION TO STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article talks about cooperation between school, family and community in providing ecological legal education to students.*

Keywords: *ecological and legal education and upbringing in the family, students, nature, ecological laws, demographic characteristics, ecological characteristics.*

During the years of independence, our country has been paying special attention to the issue of education and upbringing of our youth. It is known that on the initiative of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, 2012 was declared the "Year of the Strong Family" and that this year is named as such, and it is also a requirement to carry out environmental and legal education and upbringing in the family at the level of modern requirements. is enough.

On February 7, 2018, under the chairmanship of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, a meeting dedicated to the issues of comprehensive support for women and strengthening of the family institution was held. "In it, the women's committee, neighborhood and other public organizations have been limited to holding various events and meetings over the years, and have been effective in providing real assistance to families, women and young girls in difficult social situations didn't go. As a result of this, many issues have been accumulated in the localities, and no clearly targeted work has been carried out to solve them," it was emphasized.

"It is important to pay more attention to the life problems of our young people, to increase the number of modern jobs suitable for them, to support their noble aspirations and initiatives, innovative ideas, and to improve the social and household conditions of our young generation from now on, it will be the most basic and crucial task of all levels of government agencies," President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said.

This idea is to prevent environmental problems in our country, to improve environmental legislation, to ensure environmental safety, and to make extensive use of the experience of foreign countries in this regard, to rationally use and protect natural resources, and to further increase the environmental and legal education of students concerned.

In particular, the Law "On State Policy Regarding Youth" adopted by the Legislative Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 12, 2016, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 2, 2018 "Supporting Women and Girls" According to the 2018 decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "On measures to fundamentally improve the activities in the field of support and strengthening of the family institution", the adoption of the "Concept for the Development of the Environmental Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan" especially the adoption of the "Concept of Improving Legal Culture in Society" approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.

PF-5618 dated January 9, 2019, indicates that the work being carried out in this regard is defined as one of the main directions of state policy.

Today, a separate decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to fundamentally improve the preschool education system" was adopted, and in it the following series related to the provision of environmental and legal education to students the existence of shortcomings was recognized:

first, the current state of pre-school education management does not allow timely identification and elimination of systemic problems, development and introduction of modern technologies in this field, including the non-state sector;

secondly, public-private partnership mechanisms aimed at attracting investments in the field of preschool education, including the establishment of social and universal preschool educational institutions, their material and technical re-equipment, and the use of advanced pedagogical technologies, have not been introduced;

thirdly, the current state of the infrastructure and material and technical base of preschool educational institutions does not allow to ensure full coverage of children in preschool educational institutions, the growth of the population in the country leads to overcrowding of some preschool educational institutions;

fourth, preparation of teaching-methodical, didactic (including games and toys) materials and fiction that reflect national cultural-historical values and arouse interest in reading books from childhood, and pre-school education implementation works of institutions do not meet modern requirements;

fifthly, the current system of personnel training and retraining cannot provide the field of preschool education with highly qualified specialists who are able to solve the issues of raising and comprehensive development of children at a professional level;

sixthly, the low level of the financial incentive system for the employees of pre-school educational institutions does not allow attracting qualified personnel;

seventh, shortcomings in the organization of the work of regional health authorities on providing medical services to children in pre-school educational institutions, protecting the life and health of children, including ensuring healthy nutrition it was specifically shown that it leads to a decrease in the effectiveness of preventive measures.

Today, the President aims to educate young people in the spirit of loyalty to the ideals of patriotism and national independence, to make them well-rounded individuals in all respects, as well as to develop spiritual and moral qualities in students based on our rich scientific, cultural and spiritual heritage, national and universal values. he emphasized the organization of the oriented pedagogical process on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies.

Based on the above-mentioned conceptual idea, it is shown on the basis of the model that providing environmental and legal education and training to schoolchildren will be carried out in the following directions:

1. Conducting ecological and legal education and upbringing in the family helps young people to love nature, the natural environment and its resources, to form the initial environmental legal awareness, thinking and concepts of protection and rational use of it.

In the words of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "a new system has been created that serves to analyze, monitor and evaluate the current situation, and to increase the well-being of the family through scientific research."

Of course, we still need to do a lot to improve the content, quality and effectiveness of the measures defined in this regard. Today, programs such as "Prosperous village" and "Prosperous neighborhood", "Youth are our future", and "Every family is an entrepreneur" are important because they are aimed at the same goals.

2. Environmental-legal education and upbringing in pre-school educational institutions indicates that young children's environmental-legal consciousness and thinking towards the family is well formed. At this age, our children can understand the consequences of their actions, good and bad. Also, creating a system of new generation legal textbooks and training manuals. After all, this process is a continuation of positive psychological-pedagogical conditions in the family and helps to strengthen the implementation of environmental-legal education and upbringing in the family.

3. During the school period, our young people clearly understand themselves in the state of balance between "nature, society, man and technology". They connect the knowledge of other subjects acquired in grades 1-9 with environmental-legal education and training. In particular, students of this age learn the requirements of nature and ecological laws. Therefore, when conducting environmental-legal education and upbringing of students in the family, it is necessary to take into account demographic, migration, economic-territorial (geographical) and ecological characteristics.

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